

Effectiveness of the Civil-Military Relations Strategies Adopted by Nigerian Army in Managing the Okuama-Okoloba Communal Conflict in Delta State

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Abstract

This study appraises the effectiveness of the Civil-Military Relations (CMR) strategies adopted by Nigerian Army in managing the Okuama - Okoloba communal conflict in Delta State, Nigeria. The objectives were to identify the CMR strategies used, analysis perceptions of the communities and the effectiveness of these CMR strategies in fostering peace and security. The study was underpinned on Conflict Transformation Theory. The study adopted a survey design. The total population for this study was 4,185, comprising adult residents of the Okuama and Okoloba communities, as well as personnel from the Directorate of Army Public Relations. From this population, a sample of 351 respondents was selected using the Krejcie and Morgan sample size determination table. Structured questionnaire and in-depth interviews were primary instruments for data collection, while descriptive statistics were used for data analysis. Findings reveal that the Nigerian Army employed multi-dimensional CMR strategies including joint community–security collaboration, information sharing, dialogue/mediation sessions, and humanitarian interventions such as medical outreach and distribution of relief items. These strategies were moderately effective in reducing tensions and restoring short-term peace, but their impact on long-term trust and sustainable community-military relations was limited. The effectiveness was largely associated with operational coordination rather than relationship-building, and community perceptions remained mixed due to limited dialogue, weak civil engagement, and occasional use of coercive measures. The study concluded that while the Army’s CMR strategies achieved immediate stabilisation, they were insufficient for fostering sustainable peace. It recommends strengthening dialogue and mediation mechanisms, enhancing consistent community engagement, improving civil-military coordination and expanding non-kinetic interventions to build trust and promote long-term stability in communal conflict management.

Keywords: Civil-Military Relations, Communal Conflict, Community Relations, Media Relations, Okuama and Okoloba Communities

Introduction

Civil–Military Relations (CMR) has gained recognition as a non-kinetic public relations tool used by security forces to manage communal crises and complex internal security challenges. Its importance lies in the fact that effective military operations depend not

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only on the use of force but also on securing public trust, support and cooperation through constructive engagement (Michelsen & Colley, 2018). Modern security governance situates military institutions within a communication and relational environment where credibility, reputation management, and relationship-building are essential for operational success.

Globally, militaries employ CMR strategies such as community engagement, dialogue, mediation, humanitarian support, and medical outreach to build public goodwill during peacekeeping operations (Onyeka & Ituen, 2018). In Europe, Bosnia, Herzegovina, and Kosovo have applied CMR strategies in multinational peace operations, while African countries like South Africa, Uganda, and Kenya adopted similar approaches to manage internal conflicts, aligning with African Union and Economic Community of West African States framework that emphasise professionalism, transparency, and public engagement (Ohazuruike, 2024).

In Nigeria, the Nigerian Army has institutionalised CMR strategies since the return of democratic government in 1999 to complement its kinetic operations to manage communal and internal security threats. Notable among the CMR activities and programmes include: community and stakeholder engagement which seeks to encourage inclusive dialogue between disputing groups, involving traditional leaders, youth groups, and local authorities to foster peace ownership (Musa & Heinecken, 2022). Mediation and dialogue sessions provide neutral platforms for negotiation, while humanitarian interventions such as relief support, medical outreach, and Quick Impact Projects including construction of boreholes, school renovations, and minor road repairs help to reduce suffering and improve perceptions of the public about military involvement in such disputes (Ibrahim, Abdullahi & Roslan, 2018).

Nevertheless, the effectiveness of CMR is often constrained by issues of mistrust, ethnic and resource-based tensions as well as complex local dynamics (Salihu, 2021). The 2024 Okuama–Okoloba conflict in Delta State, rooted in land and fishing disputes, necessitated the Nigerian Army to intervene after the failure of both traditional institutions and the Delta State government to keep the peace. The Army in its quest to ensure peace and tranquility combined kinetic operations with CMR strategies to galvanise support, acceptance and goodwill of the affected communities. Despite applying the soft actions and people-centric approach to address the crisis, challenges such as alleged human rights violations and community resistance persisted (Nenenga, 2023).

While CMR tools are recognised as effective in fostering trust and legitimacy between military forces and disputing communities (Bamidele, 2021), gaps remain in understanding how these CMR strategies shape perceptions, trust, and collaboration between troops of the Nigerian Army and communities throughout the military led-operations. This study therefore, appraise the effectiveness of the civil-military relations strategies adopted by the Nigerian Army during the Okuama–Okoloba communal conflict in order to draw lessons for future interventions.

Research Objectives

The specific objectives of the study were to:

1. Identify the civil-military relations strategies employed by the Nigerian Army in managing the Okuama - Okoloba communal conflict.
2. Find out how the Okuama and Okoloba communities perceived the civil-military relations strategies employed by the Nigerian Army in managing the conflict.
3. Examine the effectiveness of the civil-military relations strategies in fostering peace and security between the Okuama – Okoloba communities.

Conceptualisation of Civil–Military Relations

Civil–Military Relations (CMR) refers to the patterns of communication, interaction, and cooperation between the military, civilian authorities, and society (Matei, Halladay & Bruneau, 2022). It ensures that the armed forces operate under civilian control while fulfilling their roles of defending national sovereignty and maintaining internal security. CMR reflects a balance between military professionalism and civilian authority, where the military remains politically neutral and accountable to elected leaders (Neumann, 2025). In democratic systems, this balance is essential for supporting effective governance.

CMR has evolved into a strategic public relations tool that helps the military build trust, legitimacy, and cooperation with the public (Gombar, 2025). Through community engagement, information sharing, humanitarian assistance, and collaboration with local leaders, the military communicates its intentions and addresses public concerns during conflict (Umunnakwe-Okorie, 2024). Effective CMR enhances public confidence, reduces suspicion, misinformation and encourages civilian cooperation in peacebuilding. However, poor communication and weak engagement can lead to distrust and resistance, ultimately undermining the success of military operations (Cebanu & Cebotari, 2023).

Civil–Military Relations Strategies

Civil–Military Relations (CMR) strategies refer to deliberate policies, communication methods, and engagement approaches used by the military to build constructive relationships with civilians, government authorities, and other stakeholders during security operations. In conflict settings, these strategies are non-kinetic approaches that foster mutual understanding and reduce tensions (Rukavishnikov & Pugh, 2018).

In Nigeria, particularly in managing communal conflicts, CMR strategies dictate how the military engages affected communities to build trust, maintain security, and support peaceful conflict resolution (Umunnakwe-Okorie, 2024). This include community engagement, dialogue, information sharing, and humanitarian assistance aimed at promoting cooperation. Modern security operations require more than force; they rely on communication, negotiation, and community involvement to achieve sustainable peace (Sguazzini & Mazziotti di Celso, 2025). Effective CMR strategies therefore focus on structured interactions that reduce hostility, address grievances, and strengthen relationships with local leaders and stakeholders (Abalaka, Ajiteru & Sulaiman, 2025).

Conflict Management

Conflict management is the processes and strategies used to regulate, control, and resolve disputes in order to prevent it from escalating into violence (Sharbaf, Zamani & Sunyé, 2023). Conflicts are natural in human societies, often arising from differences in interests, values, beliefs or limited access to resources. Rather than eliminating conflict entirely, conflict management focuses on containing and transforming it in ways that reduce hostility and encourage constructive dialogue.

Effective conflict management addresses both the visible aspects of conflict and the underlying causes that triggers and sustain it, such as inequality or competition over resources (Mamata & Kavilal, 2025). It involves practical strategies like negotiation, mediation, arbitration, reconciliation, and broader peacebuilding efforts. The success of any conflict management depends on cooperation among the disputing actors and the establishment of mechanisms that can help build trust, foster dialogue, and support long-term peace.

Communal Conflict

Communal conflict refers to violent or non-violent disputes between groups sharing ethnic, religious, or cultural identities, often arising from competition over land, resources, political power, or longstanding grievances (Okpa, Ajah, Eze & Enweonwu, 2023). Unlike interpersonal conflicts, they involve collective identities, making them more intense and prone to escalation. They are common in multi-ethnic societies where inequality, poverty, weak governance, and political manipulation heighten tensions. Minor disputes can quickly escalate into prolonged violence due to deep-rooted mistrust and weak conflict resolution systems (Modeyin & Inobemhe, 2025). In Nigeria, communal conflicts often centred on land, chieftaincy titles, resource control, and ethnic identity which disrupt development and social cohesion (Adom & Ugal, 2025). The Okuama–Okoloba conflict in Delta State exemplifies this trend.

Civil-Military Relations Strategies in Conflict Management in Nigeria

In Nigeria, Civil–Military Relations (CMR) strategies have evolved into addressing complex security challenges which include communal clashes, insurgency, and banditry. These approaches combine kinetic operations with non-kinetic, which include public relations-driven efforts. While operations like Operation Safe Haven, Operation Delta Safe, and Operation Python Dance have help to contain violence, their long-term impacts are limited without complementary non-kinetic measures (Okoi, 2021).

To bridge this gap, the Nigerian Army adopts CMR strategies including humanitarian assistance, medical outreach, infrastructure support, and community dialogue to build trust and gain local cooperation (Nwankpa, 2021). The Nigerian Army in 2010 conceptualised CMR as a soft and people-centric approach aimed at promoting human rights, rule of law, and conflict management (Nigerian Army, 2010). However, challenges like lack of accountability, inadequate training, and poor coordination undermines the effectiveness of the CMR strategies (Eze & Ogbodo, 2022). Effective CMR which are anchored on transparency and constructive engagement remains essential for peacebuilding, legitimacy, and sustaining trust in resolving conflicts such as the Okuama -Okoloba (Smith, 2017).

Review of Empirical Works

Daniel & Ebiegberi (2024) examined civil–military relations in Nigeria from 1999 to 2024 using a mixed-method approach. Their findings show that although the military cooperated with civilian authorities in security operations, it retains significant autonomy, which weakened civilian control. The study also identified tensions arising from military involvement in internal security, unclear authority boundaries, and political interference. However, it did not explore the use of CMR strategies in conflict management.

Ohazuruike (2024) investigated civil–military relations in addressing security challenges through an exploratory and documentary design. The study disclosed that weak civilian leadership, corruption, ethnic bias, and poor accountability undermines military professionalism and limit effective responses to insecurity. It further noted that historical military involvement in politics has weakened civilian oversight and institutional transparency.

Hanağası (2022) did a study titled *State’s Soldier or Soldier’s State: A Glance at Civil-Military Relations Theory*, bordering on civil-military relations within democratic governance. The study shows that stable civil–military relations support these attributes, as the military performs best when confined to protecting the state from internal and external threats. The study further revealed that clear civilian oversight is also associated with institutional stability and societal trust.

Yaya (2021) examined civil–military relations and legislative oversight in Nigeria using secondary data. The study disclosed that there have been gradual military professionalisation since 1999 which help in improving counterinsurgency efforts. The study however highlights persistent challenges in oversight and funding as issues affecting civil–military cooperation and institutional legitimacy in the fight against insurgency. Onyeka & Ituen (2022) assessed civil-military relations and its implications on Nigeria’s national security. The study revealed that poor public cooperation, including withholding of intelligence information and hostility to the military undermines both combat and non-combat operations, thereby worsening national security.

Similarly, Omodunbi, Abodunrin, Olawole & Adeyeye (2025) examined civil-military relations in Nigeria by rethinking counter insurgency strategies. They identified use of excessive force, weak community engagement, and limited civilian oversight as factors that reduce operational success, advocating a shift to a community-based and people-centred security model. Despite these insights, none of the studies specifically examined the Okuama–Okoloba communal conflict in Delta State or assessed the effectiveness of CMR strategies in that context. This gap necessitates the present study, which focuses on evaluating the effectiveness of the CMR strategies adopted by Nigerian Army in managing the conflict.

Conflict Transformation Theory

The study is grounded in Conflict Transformation Theory, which emerged in peace and conflict studies in the late 20th century, building on earlier conflict resolution models that emphasis comprehensive, process-oriented approaches to transforming relationships and social structures (Bush & Folger, 1994). John Paul Lederach advanced the theory to address protracted social conflicts, highlighting the importance of transforming

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relationships, attitudes, and social systems rather than merely resolving surface-level disputes (Lederach, 2005). The theory focuses on long-term engagement, multi-level participation, and the inclusion of local actors, opinion leaders, and elites in peacebuilding and conflict resolution.

The key assumptions of the theory include: (1) conflict is natural and can facilitate positive social change if approached constructively; (2) conflict operate on both visible expressions and deep-rooted structural causes, requiring attention to social, political, and economic injustices; (3) sustainable peace demands relational, cultural, and institutional transformation; and (4) peacebuilding is a long-term, dialogue-driven process, championed by inclusive participation rather than coercion (Lederach, 1995, 1997; Johannesen, 2021).

The theory stresses the importance of relationships, arguing that damaged trust sustains conflicts, and that engagement must extend beyond elites to affected communities to ensure ownership and legitimacy. Temporary military interventions may halt violence but cannot achieve lasting peace if the root causes remain unaddressed. Conflict Transformation Theory is therefore, suitable for analysing the Okuama–Okoloba communal conflict, providing a lens to evaluate the Nigerian Army’s civil-military relations strategies in fostering both immediate security and long-term peace through inclusive and sustainable community engagement.

Methodology

This study employed a mixed-method approach to examine the effectiveness of civil-military relations strategies adopted by the Nigerian Army in managing the Okuama–Okoloba communal conflict. The research was conducted in the Okuama and Okoloba communities, located in Ughelli South and Bomadi Local Government Areas of Delta State, respectively. Given the complexity of the conflict and the diverse perspectives of stakeholders, the study combined quantitative survey through administration of questionnaire with qualitative in-depth interviews to capture both measurable trends and nuanced experiential insights.

The target population comprised residents of Okuama and Okoloba communities, as well as officers and soldiers of the Directorate of Army Public Relations (DAPR). Population figures included 1,255 residents of Okuama, 2,603 residents of Okoloba, and 321 officers and soldiers from DAPR, bringing the total population to 4,185 (National Bureau of Statistics, 2024; Army Headquarters DAPR nominal roll, 2025). A multistage sampling technique was employed to ensure representative selection across these groups, and a sample size of 351 was determined using Krejcie & Morgan’s formula (1970) at a 95% confidence level.

Data collection involved structured questionnaire with closed-ended questions to quantify perceptions and experiences regarding civil-military relations and conflict management. In-depth interviews were conducted with key informants from each group to provide detailed qualitative insights. The research instrument was validated by experts from the Department of Mass Communication, Reverend Father Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi. Quantitative data were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics, while qualitative interview data were subjected to thematic analysis to identify recurring patterns and themes relevant to the study objectives.

Population Size (N)	Sample Size (n)
3500	346
4000	351
4185	351
4500	354
5000	357

Source: Krejcie & Morgan (1970)

Data Presentation and Analysis

Data collected for this study are presented in the table below:

Table 1: The Civil-Military Relations Strategies used by the Nigerian Army in Managing the Okuama and Okoloba Communal Conflict (Army Personnel only)

Civil-Military Strategy	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Joint community-security collaboration and information sharing to aid Army's operations	88	27.4
Community and stakeholder engagement to gain good will and support	22	6.1
Holding of mediation and dialogue sessions between the disputing communities	10	3.1
Provision of Humanitarian and free medical outreaches	42	13.1
All of the above	159	49.5
Total	321	100

Table 1 shows that half of respondents (49.5% Nigerian Army personnel) believes that the Nigerian Army combined all civil-military relations strategies which was a multi-dimensional approaches in managing the crisis. However, (27.4%), respondents endorsed joint security and coordination while dialogue and mediation were limited with (3.1%) endorsement, highlighting the need to strengthen community engagement for sustainable conflict resolution.

Table2: Perception of CMR Strategies Employed in Managing the Conflict (N = 323)

Statement	SD f (%)	D f (%)	U f (%)	A f (%)	SA f (%)	Total
The Nigerian Army maintained open and effective communication with members of the Okuama and Okoloba communities during the conflict management process.	39 (12.1%)	58 (18.0%)	32 (9.9%)	129 (39.9%)	65 (20.1%)	323

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The civil–military engagement strategies adopted by the Nigerian Army helped to build trust between the military and the affected communities.	49 (15.2%)	65 (20.1%)	39 (12.1%)	106 (32.8%)	64 (19.8%)	323
The Nigerian Army demonstrated respect for community leaders and local cultural practices while managing the conflict.	32 (9.9%)	52 (16.1%)	45 (13.9%)	123 (38.1%)	(22.0%)	323
The Nigerian Army’s interaction with community members helped to reduce tensions between the conflicting communities.	45 (13.9%)	61 (18.9%)	36 (11.1%)	117 (36.2%)	64 (19.8%)	323
Overall, the civil–military relations strategies used by the Nigerian Army positively influenced community perceptions of the military’s role in managing the conflict.	42 (13.0%)	55 (17.0%)	32 (9.9%)	130 (40.2%)	64 (19.8%)	323

Table 2 Respondents generally perceived the Nigerian Army’s civil–military relations strategies in the Okuama–Okoloba conflict as effective, noting communication with communities, respect for leadership, and resident engagement. While many viewed these efforts as helpful in reducing tensions, some respondents remained skeptical, indicating mixed perceptions of the impact on trust and conflict resolution.

Table 3: Respondents’ rating of the Most Effective Civil Military Relations Strategies adopted by Nigerian Army in Managing the Conflict

Level of Effectiveness	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)	Rating
Joint community-security collaboration and information sharing to aid Army’s operations	105	32.5	1 st
Community and stakeholder engagement to gain good will and support	82	25.4	2 nd
Holding of Dialogue session with the communities	45	13.9	4 th
Provision of Medical and Humanitarian	65	20.1	3 rd
All of the above	26	8.1	5 th
Total	323	100	

Respondents rated joint community–security collaboration and information sharing as the most effective CMR strategy (32.5%), followed by community and stakeholder engagement (25.4%) and medical/humanitarian interventions (20.1%). Dialogue sessions

were rated lower (13.9%), and only 8.1% preferred all strategies combined. Findings suggest the Army prioritises short-term security over long-term relationship-building, highlighting the need to strengthen dialogue, deepen community engagement, and expand humanitarian efforts for sustainable peace.

Interview Response

Interviewer: *What civil-military relations strategies did the Nigerian Army adopted in managing the Okuama - Okoloba communal conflict in Delta State?*

Army Public Relations Officer: The civil–military relations strategies included collaboration with other security agencies, particularly the Nigeria Police Force, as well as close engagement with local authorities and community leaders. The Army also conducted dialogue and mediation meetings, medical outreaches and distribution of palliatives to build public trust, goodwill and support. These efforts, combined with visible patrols, help to stabilise the area and restore peace.

Interviewer: *How did humanitarian and social intervention provided by the Nigerian Army contributed to restoring peace and stability in the affected communities?*

Army Public Relations Officer: The Army complemented security operations with humanitarian assistance, including medical outreach and palliatives, using soft and people-centric strategies to improve its image, rebuild trust, and strengthen civil-military cooperation, portraying the force as a partner in peacebuilding rather than an aggressor.

Interviewer: *What measures were taken to ensure long-term peace and prevent future conflicts between Okuama and Okoloba people?*

Army Public Relations Officer: The Army facilitated the establishment of a joint peace committee with community and local government representatives to monitor agreements and detect early signs of tension, reflecting a sustainability strategy that promotes ongoing dialogue and conflict prevention beyond direct military intervention.

Interviewer: *What is the general perception of your community to the civil–military relations strategies employed by the Nigerian Army in managing the conflict?*

Okuama Community Leader: Okuama community members acknowledged the Army’s engagement and humanitarian support, but persistent concerns over soldiers’ treatment of civilians’ limited trust, leaving many residents skeptical of the Army’s intentions despite its outreach efforts.

Okoloba Community Leader: From our side, the Army made efforts to communicate with our leaders and involve us in the peace process. The meetings and discussions they

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held help to reduce tension between the two communities. Many people in Okoloba felt the Army respected our traditional leaders and listened to our concerns. Although there is still room for better engagement, most residents believe the Army's actions helped restore peace in the area.

Interviewer: How will you rate the Effectiveness of the Army's conflict management strategies?

Okuama Community Leader: The Army's engagement and humanitarian efforts were partly appreciated, particularly medical and relief support, but perceptions of bias and unequal treatment undermined trust. This highlights that, despite short-term benefits, sustained and impartial engagement is needed to build lasting confidence and credibility with the communities.

Okoloba Community Leader: The dialogue and mediation approach used by the Army was commendable. There were series of consultations and constructive discussions between communities facilitated by the Army which contributed significantly to the current peace we are experiencing. Timely and professional intervention prevented escalation, with their presence and management of the conflict viewed as crucial in stabilising the situation.

Discussion of Findings

The study reveals that the Nigerian Army employed a range of Civil–Military Relations (CMR) strategies in managing the Okuama–Okoloba communal conflict, with joint community–security collaboration, humanitarian assistance, community engagement, and dialogue initiatives being the most prominent. Nearly half of the respondents (49.5%) indicated that the Army adopted a combination of these strategies, reflecting a multidimensional approach to conflict management. This aligns with Hanağası (2022), who emphasises that effective civil–military relations combine operational and engagement approaches to address complex conflicts. It also supports the view that conflict management requires both enforcement and community-focused strategies to promote cooperation and stability. However, the findings indicate uneven emphasis across strategies. Joint community–security collaboration and information sharing received the highest recognition, while mediation and dialogue initiatives were the least cited. This suggests that operational priorities focused more on short-term stabilisation rather than sustained dialogue-based conflict resolution, which consistent with Salihu (2021), who notes that military institutions often prioritise intelligence and control in conflict situations.

Findings further indicate that many community members perceived the Army's engagement as effective, particularly in communication, respect for local leadership, and stakeholder consultation. This supports Onyeka & Ituen (2022), who argue that effective civil–military relations enhance public cooperation and trust. However, some respondents expressed concerns about fairness and possible bias, indicating mixed perceptions. Community leaders acknowledged the value of humanitarian support and dialogue but

noted that certain aspects of military conduct created unease, reinforcing Musa & Heineken's (2022) view that unprofessional behaviour can undermine trust.

Additionally, respondents rated joint community-security collaboration as the most effective strategy, followed by community engagement and humanitarian interventions. This highlights the importance of coordination and information sharing in stabilising conflict areas, consistent with Abalaka, Ajiteru & Sulaiman (2025), who emphasise collaborative engagement as key to operational effectiveness.

Interview findings further underscore the significance of soft-power strategies. Medical outreaches and distribution of relief materials were identified as critical in presenting the military as a partner in peacebuilding, supporting Gombar (2025), who highlights the role of humanitarian initiatives in building legitimacy and public confidence. From the perspective of Conflict Transformation Theory, the findings suggest that while the Army's interventions contributed to immediate stability, they were more focused on short-term conflict management than long-term transformation. The limited emphasis on sustained dialogue and structured mediation indicates the need for stronger engagement mechanisms that promote reconciliation, trust-building, and lasting peace.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study concludes that Nigerian Army's Civil–Military Relations strategies restored short-term peace through security collaboration, humanitarian support, and information sharing, but limited dialogue and engagement left trust and long-term reconciliation weak, highlighting the need for sustained community-focused interventions. Based on the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. The Nigerian Army should strengthen dialogue, mediation, and structured community engagement to build trust, address grievances and correct perceptions.
2. The Nigerian Army should enhance personnel training in communication, negotiation, cultural sensitivity, and conflict transformation, while ensuring strict professional conduct to prevent abuses and rebuild trust with affected communities.
3. The Nigerian Army should strengthen collaboration with traditional leaders, community groups, and civil authorities to ensure inclusive decision-making and shared ownership of peace processes.
4. The Nigerian Army should expand and consistently implement medical, relief, and infrastructural interventions to build goodwill, reduce hostility, and complement security efforts with lasting community benefits.

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